

Paper 11**E-NAM: A BETTER HOPE FOR THE FARMERS****Vinutha H. K ¹, Savitha Kotian P ² & Shruthi S Dange ³**Faculty & Research Scholar of Institute of Management and Commerce,
Srinivas University, Mangalore.Orcid ID: 0000-0002-4583-0572, E-mail: vinutha.srinivasuniversity@gmail.com

Faculty of Sri Mahaveera College, Moodabidri.

Orcid ID: 0000-0001-5278-9013, E-mail: savithakotian819@gmail.com

Faculty of Sri Mahaveera College, Moodabidri.

Orcid ID: 0000-0003-2946-7205, E-mail: shruthisdange@gmail.com

Corresponding Author Contact Number – 8050813931

ABSTRACT

Electronic National Agriculture Markets (e-NAM) is an online agricultural commodity trading platform in India. Many farmers in the country are not able to enjoy the rewards of their labour because middlemen victimise them. However, e-NAM, a government-launched online market launched in 2016, holds the promise of increasing farmers' earnings by connecting them directly to buyers across the country. As a result, the government intends to double farmer income in the near future. This article emphasizes the enhanced integration of APMCs across the country through a common online market platform that enables pan-India trade in agricultural commodities, better value discovery through a transparent auction process based on produce quality, timely online payment to the farmer's bank account, and reduced chances of collusion among traders. The study concludes that e-NAM will provide significant benefits in the near future through higher returns to farmers, lower transaction costs to buyers, and stable prices and availability to consumers.

Keywords: E-NAM, APMC, online market, farmers, pan-India, online payment.

1. INTRODUCTION:

The Electronic National Agriculture Market (eNAM) is a trading portal that connects existing APMC markets across India to form a unified national market for agricultural commodities. Initially, e-NAM trade began within the individual e-NAM mandi (market), with farmers and traders from that mandi participating. On 14 April 2016, Prime Minister of India, Sri Narendra Modi, launched it by the Ministry of Agriculture, Government of India. During the UPA's tenure, the Congress government in Karnataka launched a similar project, which was a huge success [1]. The NDA government has implemented it on a national scale. The goal is to provide farmers with relief and to close the gap between farms and mandis. This step could be viewed as a step toward reducing farmer suicide [2]. It is a pan-India initiative aimed at ensuring transparency in agricultural commodity buying and selling. This can be viewed as a tool that will aid in the development of a national network of physical mandis that can be accessed online [3].

2. LITERATURE REVIEW:

E-NAM is an online trading method that allows farmers to trade their agricultural products without the involvement of middlemen. Many scholars shared their thoughts on E-NAM and its impact on farmers. A number of scholars have contributed to the study of E-NAM and its implementation, as shown in the table below. Table 1: Exhibits the contribution by different authors on E-NAM and its impact on farmers

Sl. No	Focus	Outcome	References
1	Agricultural marketing reforms	An understanding of willingness to pay for green products is developed in this study. Marketers have recognised the significance of determining consumers' willingness to pay (WTP) before introducing green products to various target audiences. The goal of this paper is to look at how consumers' behaviours and environmental locus of control affect their willingness to pay for green products.	[1]
2	Adoption of E-NAM platform	The study contributes to a better understanding of adopters' online habits and helps to bring more participants to the National Agricultural Marketing B2B platform, ensuring its eventual success.	[2]
3	e-NAM Awareness	The majority of farmers had a basic understanding of how e-NAM operated. Education, extension interaction, marketing capability, revenue orientation, mass publicity, contingency position, and socialisation all had a significant impact on knowledge scores.	[3]
4	Online interconnectivity of e-mandies	The government decided to create this e-platform for farmers to meet the needs of each state in order to	[4]

		remove inter-state obstacles in transferring farm produce. e-NAM has the ability to transform the Indian agriculture market from one of tradition to one of innovation by allowing farmers to shift their crops.	
5	Constraints faced by the Farmers	Within the State, market fragmentation restricts the free movement of agricultural goods, and numerous different processing of agri-produce and various layers of mandi charges end up raising consumer prices while providing no comparable benefit to farmers.	[5]
6	Functioning of e-NAM	eNAM contributes to the government's "ONE NATION ONE MARKET" goal. As a result, the goal of this research paper will be to investigate the operation, implementation, and status of eNAM in Rajasthan, in addition to conduct research on the SWOC evaluation of eNAM policy.	[6]
7	Increase in Farmer's Income	The establishment of eNAM is a landmark initiative that will undoubtedly help to strengthen the agricultural marketing sector and increase farmers' income.	[7]

3. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

- To understand the emerging trends in the existing market launched by the Central Government.
- To study the operation of eNAM
- To explore the key benefits of eNAM implementation on farmers.
- To look into the impact of eNAM on other beneficiaries.

4. METHODOLOGY:

For the purpose of present study, mainly literature survey and secondary data has been used. The required secondary data was collected from various journals, articles, eNAM helpline and from related websites.

5. WHAT IS ENAM?

The Electronic National Agricultural Market (eNAM) is an online trading platform in India for agricultural commodities. Farmers, traders, and buyers can trade commodities online through the market. It provides a single point of contact for all APMC (Agriculture Produce Marketing Committees) information and services. This includes trade offers to buy and sell, provision to respond to trade offers, and commodity arrivals and prices. While the online market reduces transaction costs and information asymmetry, agricultural produce will continue to be transported via mandis. The Small Farmers' Agribusiness Consortium (SFAC), a registered society of the Department of Agriculture, Cooperation, and Farmers' Welfare, manages eNAM (DACFW).

- State authorities grant traders/buyers and commission agents licences without requiring physical presence or possession of a shop/premises in the market yard.
- A trader's unified licence is valid across all markets in the state [8].
- Harmonisation of agricultural produce quality standards and provision of assaying (quality testing) infrastructure in all markets to allow buyers to bid with confidence [9].
- Market fee levied at a single point, i.e. on the first wholesale purchase from the farmer.
- Provision of Soil Testing Laboratories in/near the selected mandi to allow visiting farmers to use this facility in the mandi [10].

6. BENEFITS OF ENAM:

- Complete transparency eliminates the possibility of intentional or unintentional manipulation of the tendering / auctioning process.
- Farmers can sell their products without the involvement of brokers or middlemen, resulting in competitive returns on their investment [11].
- Encourages real-time price discovery based on current demand and supply.
- Promotes online payment and the availability of higher-quality produce at more affordable prices to consumers [12, 17].
- Producers will benefit from higher price realisation.
- Buyers' transaction costs are reduced.
- It improves commodity supply chain efficiency and reduces waste [13].

7. CHALLENGES OF E-NAM

- Governments are experiencing troubles in trying to convince all stakeholders, such as farmers, traders, and others are migrating to the online platform.
- There is no indication that farmers have benefited from this new system in terms of lower commissions to traders or higher returns on their produce [14].
- Poor system and low utilisation of advancement
- Asymmetry of information and the cloud process for esteem revelation

- Increased feature fees
- Enhancement controls [15, 18].

8. SUGGESTIONS:

- a) Regulatory Body for settlement of disputes.
- b) Extend credit facilities to the farmers based on their agriculture produce and repayment is made as and when the income is generated.
- c) Motivate non-farmers to involve in agricultural business.
- d) Agricultural department must conduct various awareness programmes periodically.
- e) Proper warehousing facilities should be provided.
- f) Expand their APMC towards supplying of agricultural inputs.
- g) Uninterrupted and low cost internet connectivity in market.
- h) Alleviate fear of taxation among traders and APMC.
- i) Bankers and NGO's should try to motivate farmers to make use of e-NAM.
- j) Provision to be made for blacklisting defaulters (traders) into entire e-NAM system.

9. CONCLUSION:

The success of E-NAM is dependent on how well farmers benefit from this scheme. To achieve e-market success, they must satisfy the competing interests of all participants (farmers, traders, and APMC); if one group is dissatisfied with e-markets, the entire system will fail. The price information generated by APMC can be disseminated through all information bulletins, TV channels, and scrolling, and used as a benchmark price for other non-e-markets [19].

A significant challenge for the government would be to integrate all states and persuade them to implement this policy. If fully implemented, this policy will result in a major reform that will permanently transform the agricultural sector [20].

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